

Centre of Excellence in Simulation of Weather and Climate in Europe
Phase 2

Initial Release of ESDM-PAV runtime

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Table of Contents

1. Introduction	3
2. Software architecture	3
3. First release of the ESDM PAV	4
3.1. ESDM PAV Experiment Schema	4
3.2. ESDM PAV Python Client	6
3.3. ESDM PAV Runtime	7

1. Introduction

This document serves as an interim report for the implementation activities, and the related software release, concerning the Earth System Data Middleware (ESDM) interface for supporting data-intensive *post-processing, analytics* and *visualisation* (PAV). In particular, this report provides a summary of the development activities carried out for the first software release of the ESDM PAV runtime. The initial version of the software, released at M21 of the ESIWACE2 project, focuses on the first version of the runtime environment and the tools for interacting with it, i.e., the ESDM PAV Python client. Besides this, other activities concerning the software release have also been addressed, such as the setup of the repositories and the initial documentation.

2. Software architecture

Starting from the ESDM PAV (Figure 1) design introduced in ESIWACE2 milestone MS5.1¹, and further refined in milestone MS4.1², the first release aims at providing an initial operational version of the ESDM PAV runtime and related libraries and clients to develop and execute PAV experiments. This version supports the execution of both Ophidia and CDO operators, as well as other generic command line tools.

Figure 1. Refined ESDM PAV software architecture

¹ ESIWACE2 Architecture Milestone MS5.1: <https://zenodo.org/record/3592385>

² ESIWACE2 ESDM Architecture Milestone MS4.1: <https://zenodo.org/record/3724217>

3. First release of the ESDM PAV

The following subsections describe the state, at the time of the first release, of the main components of the ESDM PAV and summarize the implementation activities carried out until this first release. Further details concerning the design can be found in MS4.1 and MS5.1.

3.1. ESDM PAV Experiment Schema

The ESDM PAV *experiment schema* has been defined in order to support the definition and execution of PAV experiments composed of different tools. It represents the experiment definition language providing the constructs for specifying PAV workflows in terms of tasks and dependencies. Users and developers can create PAV experiment documents by exploiting this schema. The format initially adopted to implement these documents is the *JavaScript Object Notation (JSON)*, which represents a widely used language-independent format providing a flexible way for specifying data in a human-readable way. Since the PAV application requirements are similar to those of the Ophidia framework (one of the target systems to be integrated into the ESDM PAV), which has its own Workflow Management System (WMS), the format has been inspired based on the Ophidia workflow schema³.

Listing 1 shows the definition of the experiment schema supported in the first version of the ESDM PAV runtime. It shows the available abstractions to describe workflow tasks and dependencies, through a set of keywords. A workflow can be considered as a list of “*task*” JSON objects, each one consisting of the following main keywords:

- **name:** the name given to that specific task to identify it; it is a mandatory key and its value must be unique within the whole PAV document file;
- **type:** PAV tool/system to be used for the execution;
- **operator:** a mandatory field specifying the operator to be executed;
- **arguments:** an optional list of values describing the input arguments for the specified operator;
- **dependencies:** an optional list of the tasks (parents) that have to be completed before the execution of this task (child).

With respect to the version previously defined in MS4.1, the schema has been refined in order to simplify the interface; to this end the “*outputs*” and “*inputs*” keywords, defined at task level, have been moved to the level of the “*arguments*” keyword, as admissible arguments. In this way, the “input” and “output” arguments can be specified when required by the particular task using the following format shown in Listing 3 (in line 12 or 13). The rest of the schema follows the same structure defined in MS4.1. Additional keywords, such as “*abstract*”, are also available to describe the overall experiment workflow.

```
1  {
2    "schema": "http://json-schema.org/draft-04/schema#",
3    "title": "pav_experiment_schema",
4    "description": "PAV Experiment Document JSON Schema",
```

³ Ophidia JSON Request Schema: http://ophidia.cmcc.it/documentation/users/appendix/json_request.html

```

5   "type": "object",
6   "properties":
7   {
8     "name": {"type": "string", "description": "experiment name"},
9     "author": {"type": "string", "description": "experiment author"},
10    "abstract": {"type": "string", "description": "experiment
description"},
11    "nthreads": {"type": "string", "description": "number of threads for
the entire experiment"},
12    "tasks":
13    {
14      "type": "array",
15      "description": "task list representing the experiment",
16      "items":
17      {
18        "type": "object",
19        "description": "task with its properties",
20        "properties":
21        {
22          "name": {"type": "string", "description": "unique task name"},
23          "type": {"type": "string", "description": "type of PAV tool to
run"},
24          "operator": {"type": "string", "description": "Operator name"},
25          "arguments": { "type": "array",
26            "description": "list of user-defined operator arguments as
key=value pairs",
27            "items": {"type": "string", "description": "format to use:
keyX=valueX"},
28            "uniqueItems": true},
29          "dependencies":
30          {
31            "type": "array",
32            "description": "list of tasks on which the current task
depends",
33            "items":
34            {
35              "type": "object",
36              "description": "dependency for a specific argument of the
current task",
37              "properties":
38              {
39                "task": {"type": "string", "description": "task name
which the current argument depends on"},
40                "argument": {"type": "string", "default": "cube",
"description": "argument name depending on the output of the task
specified in 'task' field"}
41              },
42              "required": ["task"]

```

```

43         },
44         "uniqueItems": true
45     }
46 },
47     "required": ["name", "operator"],
48     "additionalProperties": false
49 },
50     "minItems": 1,
51     "uniqueItems": true
52 }
53 },
54 "required": ["name", "tasks"],
55 "additionalProperties": false
56 }

```

Listing 1. Definition of ESDM PAV Schema

3.2. ESDM PAV Python Client

The ESDM PAV Client is a Python module providing the features to model and execute a PAV experiment implemented with the aforementioned experiment schema. The module is available on Github at <https://github.com/OphidiaBigData/esdm-pav-client>. The main features provided by the module are:

- *The API for creating PAV experiments*: it implements two classes (i.e., *Workflow* and *Task*) and a set of methods to help users create a PAV workflow, handle the underlying ESDM PAV schema transparently and make sure that the proper syntax and rules are followed. Moreover, it implements the methods to load and store the *experiment document* as a JSON file;
- *A method and a command line interface for the submission*: it provides a method for submitting the defined PAV workflow directly from a Python script or notebook, as well as a CLI for submitting an experiment document. The method and the client interact with the ESDM PAV runtime for the execution of the experiment and take care of substituting the argument at execution time. The Python client has been implemented in place of a C-based one in order to improve tool portability and usability, and to avoid having to build the code in each environment. The communication between the PAV Python client and the PAV runtime is based on a TCP/IP architecture inherited from the Ophidia Server (see Section 3.3), exploiting PyOphidia features for the client-side.

Listing 2 shows a usage example of this python module for the definition of a simple experiment workflow composed of four tasks (i.e., a CDO and three Ophidia operators). It first specifies a post-processing operation with CDO (a regridding on a NetCDF file), then it imports the data in Ophidia to perform a statistical analysis (calculating the moving average over 7 time steps) and finally exports the results from Ophidia into a NetCDF file. It is important to note that the value *\$1* associated with the “*ncores*” argument will be replaced at submission time with the value specified at job submission (line 27), the value is 2 in this case. Additional usage examples can be found in the module documentation⁴.

⁴ ESDM PAV Python Client readme: <https://github.com/OphidiaBigData/esdm-pav-client/blob/master/README.md>

```

1  from esdm_pav_client import Workflow
2
3  w1 = Workflow(name="CDO and Ophidia PAV experiment example",
4               author="ESiWACE2",
5               abstract="Example of PAV workflow with CDO and Ophidia")
6  t1 = w1.newTask(name="Regrid",
7                 type="cdo",
8                 operator='-remapbil,grid_file',
9                 arguments={'input': 'path/to/infile.nc', 'output':
10                            'path/to/outfile.nc'})
11 t2 = w1.newTask(name="Import",
12                type="ophidia",
13                operator='oph_importnc',
14                arguments={'measure': "pr", 'ncores': '$1'},
15                dependencies={t1:'input'})
16 t3 = w1.newTask(name="Moving avg",
17                type="ophidia",
18                operator='oph_apply',
19                arguments={'query': 'oph_moving_avg(measure, 7)',
20                            'measure_type': 'auto', 'ncores': '$1'},
21                dependencies={t2:'cube'})
22 t4 = w1.newTask(name="Export",
23                type="ophidia",
24                operator='oph_exportnc2',
25                arguments={'output': 'path/to/outfile.nc'},
26                dependencies={t3:'cube'})
27
28 w1.save("example.json")
29 w1.submit("2") # Submits the workflow and substitutes the parameter $1
30                in the arguments, e.g., Line 13 and Line 18

```

Listing 2. Simple PAV experiment implemented with the ESDM PAV Python module

The current version also provides the Python scripts to easily install the module, as well as the inline documentation and unit testing for the main methods. Next releases of the module, besides the improvement of these methods, will include additional functionalities for monitoring the experiment execution status and managing its execution.

3.3. ESDM PAV Runtime

The ESDM PAV runtime is a C-based system designed to execute experiments modelled with the ESDM PAV schema (defined in the previous section). The runtime environment takes care of: parsing and validating the experiment document to verify if the file follows the syntax and workflow definition rules; building the corresponding execution graph based on the experiment specifications; mapping the tasks to the related command and submitting their execution in the proper order and according to the dependencies; and monitoring the execution of the whole experiment workflow. The runtime is able to handle not only a sequence of tasks, but also more complex Directed Acyclic Graph (DAG) tasks.

The ESDM PAV runtime system can already handle experiments using the full set of keywords and constructs defined in the aforementioned schema; future versions will support additional constructs to

enhance experiment execution. Moreover, future releases will also include features to monitor the execution progress and status.

Since the experiment schema has been defined based on the workflow schema already developed for the Ophidia framework, part of the code of the runtime environment is based on the Ophidia Server WMS engine. This design choice has allowed us to reduce the time-to-solution and develop a first version of the runtime which is more robust and capable of handling much more complex workflow structures. From an implementation standpoint, the ESDM PAV runtime is able to operate without interacting with the data management system adopted by Ophidia for the system catalog (MySQL-based) and required by Ophidia Server to handle tasks, users, work sessions and the interaction with Ophidia framework, which also accesses the catalog. In fact, the runtime system is based on a simple SQLite database, only accessed by the module. This database is mainly used to store information on task status used by the WMS. Note that, despite these modifications, the ESDM PAV runtime inherits all the interfaces of Ophidia Server (e.g., SOAP, WPS, GSI, etc.) and, therefore, it can interact with legacy Ophidia client applications, e.g., the Terminal and PyOphidia).

The current version of the runtime engine can support the execution of PAV workflows on a single-node, where tasks are spawned as new processes on the node resources. Future versions will also include the possibility to execute tasks over multiple nodes on a HPC-infrastructure, supporting the integration with different resource managers, such as LSF or Slurm. The code is publicly available on Github at <https://github.com/OphidiaBigData/esdm-pav-runtime>.

As depicted in Figure 1, the runtime system is designed to support, and to be easily extended with, additional PAV tools and software through the definition of plugins. The current version is able to support both Ophidia and CDO operators along with other command line-based tools through a generic plugin; the integration of visualisation tools for offline analysis will be addressed in next releases. Nevertheless, thanks to the generic plugin, an initial integration of ParaView in PAV workflow, through a script for non-interactive visualisation, is already possible and has been successfully tested with the current version.

Some adaptations have also been implemented in the Ophidia framework in order to adhere to the ESDM PAV schema. In particular, the “input” and “output” argument names have been added to the Ophidia import and export operators to provide a similar interface for all the tasks working on input and output files (i.e., CDO and Ophidia). Besides this, a specific plugin for CDO operators has also been implemented based on the notification-based approach already used by the Ophidia operators, in order to communicate the execution status to the runtime engine. The Ophidia extensions have been implemented in the Ophidia repositories development branches.

Listing 3 shows an example of a PAV experiment document following the aforementioned schema. This example implements the same experiment defined in Listing 2 from the perspective of the PAV document.

```
1  {
2    "name": "CDO and Ophidia PAV experiment example",
3    "author": "ESiWACE2",
4    "abstract": "Example of PAV workflow with CDO and Ophidia",
```

```

5   "tasks":
6   [
7     {
8       "name": "Regrid",
9       "type": "cdo",
10      "operator": "-remapbil,grid_file",
11      "arguments": [
12        "input=path/to/infile.nc",
13        "output=path/to/outfile.nc"
14      ]
15    },
16    {
17      "name": "Import",
18      "type": "ophidia",
19      "operator": "oph_importnc",
20      "arguments": [
21        "measure=pr",
22        "ncores=$1"
23      ],
24      "dependencies": [
25        { "task": "Regrid", "argument": "input" }
26      ],
27    },
28    {
29      "name": "Moving avg",
30      "type": "ophidia",
31      "operator": "oph_apply",
32      "arguments": [
33        "query=oph_moving_avg(measure, 7)",
34        "measure_type=auto",
35        "ncores=$1"
36      ],
37      "dependencies": [
38        { "task": "Import", "argument": "cube" }
39      ]
40    },
41    {
42      "name": "Export",
43      "type": "ophidia",
44      "operator": "oph_exportnc2",
45      "arguments": [
46        "output=path/to/outfile.nc"
47      ],
48      "dependencies": [
49        { "task": "Moving avg", "argument": "cube" }
50      ]
51    }
52  ]
53 }

```

Listing 3. Example of PAV JSON document with CDO and Ophidia operators